

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Table 1S. Main linear mixed effects (LME) models statistics.

A. Random-intercept LME model for meal-related AVP dynamics					
Model formula: AVP ~ TP + BMI + (1 Participant ID)					
Predictor	β	se	t	p	d
BMI	0.01	0.03	0.20	0.842	0.05
B. Random-intercept LME model for OXT treatment-related AVP dynamics					
Model formula: AVP ~ Treatment + Visit + BMI + Treatment:Visit + (1 Participant ID)					
Predictor	β	se	t	p	d
Treatment	0.05	0.27	0.20	0.844	0.05
Visit-W4	-0.05	0.06	-0.87	0.386	0.14
Visit-W6	-0.02	0.06	-0.40	0.689	0.06
Visit-W8	0.05	0.06	0.79	0.431	0.13
BMI	0.01	0.02	0.51	0.615	0.10
C. Random-intercept LME model for OXT treatment-related sodium dynamics					
Model formula: Sodium ~ Treatment + Visit + BMI + Treatment:Visit + (1 Participant ID)					
Predictor	β	se	t	p	d
Treatment	0.14	0.52	-0.27	0.787	0.05
Visit-W2	0.95	0.38	2.49	0.014	0.40
Visit-W4	0.82	0.40	2.05	0.042	0.32
Visit-W8	0.55	0.41	1.34	0.182	0.21
BMI	-0.03	0.04	-0.75	0.457	0.20

Abbreviations: AVP, arginine vasopressin; BMI, body mass index; OXT, oxytocin; TP, time point; W, week.

Linear mixed effects (LME) model statistics (unstandardized coefficient β , its standard error, t-value, p-value, and effect size estimate Cohen's d) are presented for the following outcomes: (A.) dynamics of AVP around a standardized meal, (B.) dynamics of AVP in response to 8-week OXT treatment vs. placebo, and (C.) dynamics of sodium in response to 8-week OXT treatment vs. placebo. Model formulas are stated (e.g., "Treatment: Visit-W4" indicates a two-way interaction term of treatment [OXT vs. placebo] and study visit [week 4 vs. baseline]).

Table 2S. Exploratory linear mixed effects (LME) models including sex effects

Expl. A. Random-intercept LME model for meal-related AVP dynamics including sex effects					
Model formula: AVP ~ TP + Sex + BMI + TP:Sex + (1 Participant ID)					
Predictor	β	se	t	p	d
TP-30min	-0.09	0.10	-0.87	0.384	0.14
TP-60min	-0.06	0.10	-0.64	0.524	0.10
TP-120min	0.01	0.10	0.06	0.956	0.01
Sex	-0.19	0.28	-0.68	0.498	0.16
BMI	<0.01	0.03	0.05	0.958	0.01
TP-30min : Sex	0.04	0.14	0.26	0.798	0.04
TP-60min : Sex	-0.22	0.14	-1.52	0.131	0.24
TP-120min : Sex	-0.06	0.15	-0.41	0.680	0.07
Expl. B. Random-intercept LME model for OXT treatment-related AVP dynamics including sex effects					
Model formula: AVP ~ Treatment + Visit + Sex + BMI + Treatment:Visit + Treatment:Sex + Visit:Sex + Treatment:Visit:Sex + (1 Participant ID)					
Predictor	β	se	t	p	d
Treatment	0.29	0.37	0.80	0.430	0.21
Visit-W4	-0.07	0.08	-0.82	0.413	0.14
Visit-W6	<0.01	0.09	-0.05	0.962	0.01
Visit-W8	<0.01	0.09	0.03	0.979	<0.01
Sex	0.10	0.39	0.26	0.798	0.07
BMI	0.01	0.02	0.31	0.756	0.06
Treatment : Visit-W4	0.05	0.11	0.48	0.635	0.08
Treatment : Visit-W6	0.05	0.12	0.44	0.662	0.07
Treatment : Visit-W8	0.08	0.12	0.66	0.513	0.11
Treatment : Sex	-0.53	0.54	-0.97	0.334	0.25
Visit-W4 : Sex	0.03	0.12	0.28	0.782	0.05
Visit-W6 : Sex	-0.04	0.12	-0.32	0.748	0.05
Visit-W8 : Sex	0.10	0.13	0.78	0.435	0.13
Treatment : Visit-W4 : Sex	-0.06	0.17	-0.36	0.717	0.06
Treatment : Visit-W6 : Sex	<0.01	0.17	-0.01	0.996	<0.01
Treatment : Visit-W8 : Sex	-0.26	0.17	-1.50	0.136	0.25

Abbreviations: AVP, arginine vasopressin; BMI, body mass index; OXT, oxytocin; TP, time point; W, week.

Exploratory linear mixed effects (LME) model statistics (unstandardized coefficient β , its standard error, t-value, p-value, and effect size estimate Cohen's d) are presented for the following outcomes: (A.) dynamics of AVP around a standardized meal including sex effects, and (B.) dynamics of AVP in response to 8-week OXT treatment vs. placebo including sex effects. Model formulas are stated (e.g., "Treatment : Visit-W4 : Sex" indicates a three-way interaction term of treatment [OXT vs. placebo], study visit [week 4 vs. baseline], and sex [male vs. female]).